

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE INFORMATICS TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article analyzes modern pedagogical opportunities for improving the professional training of future computer science teachers. The digital learning environment, artificial intelligence tools, network cluster integration and the specific features of pedagogical practice are considered as the main factors in the formation of professional competencies. The article also develops existing problems and scientific and practical recommendations aimed at eliminating them.

Keywords: *professional training, computer science teacher, digital learning environment, pedagogical opportunities, artificial intelligence, network integration.*

INTRODUCTION. In the context of modernization of the education system in our country, in particular, the transition to a digital economy, new requirements are being placed on the professional training of computer science teachers. One of the priority areas of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy is the digital transformation of the personnel training system, the development of digital competencies of future specialists. In this regard, the study of pedagogical opportunities for improving the professional training of future computer science teachers is of urgent importance.

The formation of professional competencies of future computer science teachers in the process of pedagogical education includes not only the acquisition of fundamental knowledge, but also the skills of integrating modern information and communication technologies into the educational process. As researcher Qodirov BE noted, "the sufficiency of digital resources, digital competencies of students and methodological support play an important role in the development of the professional skills of a future teacher in a digital educational environment."

MAIN PART. 1. Digital learning environment is a key factor in professional training. The digital learning environment creates a unique pedagogical opportunity in improving the professional training of future computer science teachers. A modern digital learning environment serves the professional development of students by providing interactivity, flexibility and a personalized approach. The use of innovative educational exhibitions, visual materials and multimedia tools in pedagogical faculties is aimed at developing students' practical skills.

Experience shows that there are the following problems in forming students' knowledge, skills, and competencies to work in a digital learning environment:

- Insufficient provision of digital educational resources;
- lack of digital resources in the credit-module system;
- lack of programs and guidelines that teach students how to work in a digital environment.

To overcome these problems, it is advisable to introduce modern LMS platforms in higher education institutions and organize special courses on the creation and use of digital content.

2. Integration of artificial intelligence tools. The rapid development of digital technologies in the 21st century is fundamentally changing the education system. In particular, the introduction of artificial

intelligence (AI) technologies into the educational process requires new approaches to traditional teaching methods. Today, AI is not only a technical tool, but also a methodological assistant that takes the interaction between teacher and student to a new level. The main goal is to systematize advanced methodologies for using AI technologies in the educational process, analyze existing approaches, and identify ways of effective integration.

The role of artificial intelligence in education. One of the biggest advantages of artificial intelligence is the ability to implement adaptive learning. Adaptive learning systems adapt content to the student's level of knowledge, learning speed, and difficulty. Artificial intelligence is fundamentally changing the assessment process. Traditional assessment is a time-consuming and subjective process. AI, on the other hand, allows for objective, rapid, and continuous assessment. AI systems have the ability to provide real-time feedback to students. This is especially important in language learning. For example, students can interact with chatbots like ChatGPT and receive immediate feedback on grammar and communication.

The table below presents a comparative analysis of traditional and SI-based educational methodologies:

Table 1

Criteria	Traditional methodology	SI-based methodology
Approach	Same	Individualized
The role of the teacher	Knowledge transmitter	Facilitator * , mentor
Evaluation	Periodic, summative	Continuous, real-time
Content delivery	Static (textbook)	Dynamic (adaptive)
Feedback	Delayed	Instantly (real-time)

ICT has the potential to revolutionize the teaching and learning process. Research shows that the effective use of ICT depends on the following factors:

1. The priority of the pedagogical approach – SI as a technological tool should serve pedagogical goals, not vice versa.
2. Teacher development – Teachers need to be systematically trained in the use of ICT tools and develop their digital competencies. Collaborative work and school-based professional development are the most effective ways to do this.
3. Adherence to ethical principles – Clear rules and standards need to be developed to address issues such as data security, privacy, and algorithmic bias.
4. Preservation of the human factor - SI can never completely replace the teacher. Its role is to support the teacher, save his time and increase pedagogical efficiency.

There is a global trend towards integrating AI tools into pedagogical education. As part of a project implemented by the European Union in Tajikistan, special trainings have been organized for teachers on the use of AI tools (ChatGPT, Canva, HeyGen, Perplexity). This experience will expand the possibilities of using AI tools in the training of future computer science teachers. Also, a seminar on "Modern approaches to developing critical thinking in future computer science teachers" held at the Astana International University in Kazakhstan discussed the issues of integrating AI simulators into the educational process. This indicates the need to develop not only technical, but also cognitive competencies in future computer science teachers.

3. Network cluster integration - an innovative approach . The network cluster distributed integration model proposed by Mamatova Sh. F. is of great importance in training future computer science teachers in the field of programming. This model involves the creation of a "smart environment" based on the cooperation of the pedagogical university with general education schools in the region. "The network cluster integration of the pedagogical university with general education organizations in the region for joint training of students of specialized classes and future computer science teachers in the field of programming based on specially created smart environment tools gives effective results."

The use of gamification tools and personalized learning materials allows you to maintain learning motivation and effectively organize project activities.

4. The role of pedagogical practice. Pedagogical practice is an important stage in the professional training of future computer science teachers. Abdullayeva N. and Jo'rayeva G. note that "entering a real educational environment, getting acquainted with a lively group of students, participating in creating an educational environment in the classroom and at school enriches the professional competencies of a future teacher."

During the pedagogical practice, the student:

- will have the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practice;
- gains experience in working directly with educational material;
- develops skills in solving difficult situations;
- improves professional erudition.

A distinctive feature of pedagogical practice in the training of computer science teachers is that the student gains experience in using modern software tools, programming languages, and digital resources in the real educational process.

5. Application of interactive methods. Interactive teaching methods create an important pedagogical opportunity in improving the professional training of future computer science teachers. In particular, the use of interactive methods in teaching the subject "Theoretical Foundations of Computer Science" serves to form the professional competence of students.

Interactive methods:

- analysis of problem situations;
- project-based learning;
- case studies;
- role-playing games;
- brainstorming.

These methods develop students' critical thinking, creative approach, and independent decision-making skills.

6. International experiences and their application. In Europe, a new pedagogical model for training computer science teachers has been developed within the framework of the TINKER project (2024-2026). This model includes four main components:

- areas and competencies of computer science;
- authentic education;
- gender inclusion;
- teacher and professional development.

As part of the project, more than 100 educators have undergone special training and 300 teachers have received advanced training. This experience demonstrates the potential of introducing an inclusive approach and authentic education in the training of future computer science teachers in Uzbekistan.

7. Theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of professional culture . The professional training of future computer science teachers includes not only technical knowledge, but also professional culture. Professional culture is formed through the professional competencies, moral and ethical values, and reflective activity of the teacher. This is especially important for a computer science teacher, since issues of ethical standards, data security, and cyberethics are relevant when working with digital technologies. Person-centered, systematic, and cultural-contextual approaches form the methodological basis for the development of the professional culture of future computer science teachers.

CONCLUSION. The analysis of pedagogical opportunities for improving the professional training of future computer science teachers allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. The digital learning environment provides a key pedagogical opportunity for the formation of professional competencies of future computer science teachers. Therefore, it is necessary to create an infrastructure equipped with modern LMS platforms and digital resources in higher education institutions.
2. Integrating artificial intelligence tools into the learning process develops students' skills in working with modern technologies and prepares them for future professional activities.
3. The network cluster integration model enhances the practical training of future computer science teachers by strengthening cooperation between pedagogical universities and general education schools.
4. Improving pedagogical practice, increasing its duration and enriching its content will accelerate the professional adaptation of future computer science teachers.
5. It is advisable to introduce inclusive education and authentic approaches based on the study of international experiences and adaptation to the national education system.

SUGGESTIONS . As a suggestion, to improve the professional training of future computer science teachers:

- Inclusion of special courses such as "Digital Pedagogy" and "Fundamentals of Artificial Intelligence" in the curriculum;
- establishing "smart environment" laboratories in cooperation with universities and schools;
- encouraging student project activities and extensive use of gamification tools;
- It is recommended to develop inclusive education methodologies based on the study and localization of foreign experiences.

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